

Gonimbrasia belina

Mopane worm

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© B. van Asch

Group: Insect

Size: Wingspan: 10-12 cm

Distribution:

Primarily mopane woodlands in southern Africa, including South Africa, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe.

Importance:

Mopane worms are harvested from the wild at a commercial scale in southern Africa for human consumption. Demand has been increasing and harvesting and trade have intensified. Together with habitat loss and climate change, this has raised concerns about the sustainability of the species. The genome sequence will assist in understanding population dynamics and the conservation status of the species.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 34.4 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 6.65 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.4 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.4% [Single: 94.1%, Duplicated: 4.3%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 249.78 kilobases

Contig number: 6 924

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